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Transcript of talk:

*Automated mycelium microstructural characterization
with image processing artifact prediction*

Thaicia Stona de Almeida, Ph.D., Ronin Scholar

Abstract of Transcribed Presentation

This talk discusses fungal mycelium as a biomaterial, its applications, and the process of microstructure characterization based on scanning electron microscope images, the challenges of micrograph knowledge extraction and how Machine Learning can help automate the identification of imaging artifacts.

Introduction

This document contains the transcript of a talk given at the Ronin Institute Lightning Talks series in February 2024, titled *Automated mycelium microstructural characterization with image processing artifact prediction*. It presents a machine learning protocol for mycelium microstructure characterization using scanning electron microscopy images.

Transcript

[Talk starts, recording starts]

In today's talk, I would like to shortly introduce mycelium as a renewable biomaterial and go over some results on mycelium's structure characterization using machine learning. But first I want to give credit and thank the people who made the initial project possible: my former advisors doctor Prathima Nalam and doctor Olga Wodo, both at the State University of New York at Buffalo School of Engineering and Applied Sciences. And I also thank several colleagues for their contributions: from the first person to prepare the

images, Mugdha Kasarekar, to all the collaborators that I didn't have the chance to meet in person. And to Ecovative Design LCC, which provided the samples that were shared with us so that we could explore and extract lots of data about the mycelium structure.

Mycelium is the name given to the root system of mushrooms. When we think of a mushroom, we typically picture an organism with a little hat on the top, but rarely we have the chance to see what the mushroom looks in its basis. The fungi studied in this research is the *Ganoderma resinaceum*, a wood-decaying fungi without a stem. When lab-grown, using a mix of agricultural waste, nutrients and a liquid *Ganoderma* mycelium starter, the mycelium grows in a tray mold and looks like a pillow.

[slide shows figure 1]

Figure 1: From reference [3], a tray of lab-grown mycelium.

Mycelium consists of microfibers made of biopolymers, such as lipids, chitin and glycoproteins. It can be used as a programmable biomaterial, substituting styrofoam in packaging, as leather, as architectural materials, and even food. The porous nature of the mycelium creates a mesh that resembles an open cell foam structure. Being a natural microporous material, mycelium has great potential for applications in high performance filtration membranes.

The initial motivation of this study was to characterize the microstructure of mycelium, having in mind the application of mycelium as a filtration membrane. For this, it is necessary to understand the porosity of this biomaterial.

Scanning electron microscope micrographs were prepared using different parts of the

original mycelium sample. The sliced sections received a coating of gold and platinum, which minimizes the charging effects that can interfere with the SEM-imaging. Seventy images were obtained at 4 depths of mycelium growth and 3 levels of magnification. The choice of images for the present study were the youngest mycelium slices, at the top layer of the original sample, which is less dense than the older network on the base of the tray were the sample was cultivated. The 3.000X magnification provided good detail and resolution for the characterization.

The challenge of characterizing biofibrous material is that, unlike man-made electro-spun nanofibers, natural fibers tend to be complex, curly, non-linear in their features. This means that any tools for artificial fiber characterization based on images will fail to capture the tortuosity and other details of the natural network. I tried to experiment with different image filters to segment the image from scratch, but it was not successful.

[slide shows figure 2]

Figure 2: Experiments with ImageJ filters for mycelium segmentation.

ImageJ was the software chosen to segment the images, using the extensions DiameterJ for specific characterization of fibrous microstructures. DiameterJ was designed to extract

features from electrospun nanofibers. Using this tool for mycelium came with lots of supervised steps and manual classification of the micrographs

The process of image segmentation and feature extraction is automated in the beginning, when several filters designed for artificial fibers are applied for all images, creating 15 segmented images for each original SEM micrograph. It is then necessary that a trained researcher visually inspects the segmented images and decides what is the best segmentation. If, such adequate segmentation is found, we can proceed to the next phase, when DiameterJ extracts several features from the image.

Now we should note that the mycelium network is a 3-dimensional mesh that ideally should be characterized with a tomography type of method that can actually capture all 3-dimensions. That is not what scanning electron micrographs can give us, so this study is already limited by the 2-dimensional nature of the images. Also, estimating depth in a SEM micrograph can be challenging, since depth is not related to intensity of light in the image: it is the quality of the metallic coating that will determine the brightness of the image.

The automated segmentation can both miss real features and create artificial ones, adding uncertainty to the characterization process. For example, several artificial pores were created by the segmentation, pores that are artifacts of the algorithm.

We obtained a distribution of pore area that was very heavy on small pores, pores that were excessively small, below $0.4\mu m^2$. After more detailed inspection, we noticed that these pores were near the lower limit of accurate resolution. After several discussions and attempts to understand the skewness of the distribution, we decided to set cut-off limits and ignore pores below $0.4\mu m^2$, and larger than $20\mu m^2$.

I decided to inspect the pore map associated to the best segmentation and manually classify the artifact pores. I explored the set of pore features that DiameterJ extracted for the image, and found that they were enough correlated for me to try to cluster and reduce the dimension of the feature space.

When I compared the principal components plot of the clusters, I realized that there was a pattern, and it was acceptable to pick pore area and pore roundness as two sufficiently

independent features that explained the PC plot and the clusters. Adding the labels to the plot, I could retrieve which points corresponded to the artifacts, and most artifacts were found within a small area that roughly corresponded to very small and round pores. The densities of pore area of each cluster also separate well the few large pores as outliers, many small pores that included sizes below the cut-off, and an intermediate cluster of reasonable size pores.

I compared the cluster densities to the density of all images at 3.000X magnification with cut-off but no artifact identification. Setting the densities on the same scale, it is visible that the clustering can help further sanitize the data, splitting the manual selection into a cluster that contains very small pores and most of the remaining artifacts, while the medium-size pore cluster is mostly composed of actual pores, and few artifacts.

[slide shows figure 3]

Figure 3: Similarity of cluster distribution on principal component plots for different SEM micrographs at same depth and resolution.

Summarizing these results, which focused on artifacts of only one micrograph but, feature benchmark estimated for the whole set of images at same scale and depth: the researchers' choice of cut-off helps eliminating artifacts and removes the skewness of the data, which could be explained by pore detection too close to the limit of the resolution capabilities of the software. But the additional application of k-means on the feature space confirms the cut-off and enhances the identification of artifact pores.

This is a result valid for this given set of *Ganoderma resinaceum* micrographs at 3.000X magnification and good quality of coating for obtaining great quality SEM micrographs. But the visible stability of clustering, principal components and similarity of feature distribution suggests that this protocol can be adopted to automatically remove artifacts after automated segmentation and feature extraction from the mycelium micrographs, and potentially be a method to be generalized and benchmarked for larger collections of micrographs.

Other limitations of the protocol that deserve attention are related to the human factor: the decision of best segmentation and the classification of pores to define the predictor of artifacts are two factors that rely on human judgement. One question is if all segmented fibers should be included as representative fibers, even if the observer interprets from the micrograph sense of depth that the fiber is too deep in the background to be included in the final segmentation. Or should we go in the opposite direction and project all fibers in the image, collapsing the depth of the sample and ignoring the fact that the metallic coating will not reach full depth to capture the sample thoroughly?

Having considered the limitations, the presented protocol is useful in high-throughput analysis of mycelium micrographs, and helps obtaining better quality features and statistics when a full 3-dimensional analysis of the mycelium microstructure is not available.

An extended version of this work is included in the version 2 of the referred preprint, *Mining Artifacts in Mycelium SEM Micrographs*, to be submitted this February, 2024, by yours truly.

Thank you for watching my presentation.

[end of recording]

References

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